

SOCIAL SCIENCES

GARIFUNA WOMEN OF THE CARIBBEAN: AN ANALYSIS OF GENDER AND POWER

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Abstract

My research focuses on the study of Garifuna women in the Caribbean, a field of growing academic interest. This study adopts a qualitative methodological approach, focusing on the analysis of documentary sources such as academic articles, books, and historical documents, to explore the role of these women in the construction and reproduction of their communities. My goal is to make visible their historically marginalized experiences and understand the complex gender and power dynamics that affect them. Initial findings from this research highlight the multifaceted and essential role of Garifuna women as pillars of intergenerational cultural transmission. Through oral traditions, music, dance, and rituals, they preserve their language, spirituality, and ancestral traditions, exercising significant leadership in community decision-making and in family health through traditional medicine. Despite occupying central positions in the social and cultural life of their communities, Garifuna women face significant challenges such as discrimination and economic inequality. In conclusion, my research highlights the role of Garifuna women as key social actors and seeks to contribute to the promotion of public policies that guarantee equal opportunities and respect for their rights.

Keywords: woman, power, culture, generation.

Introduction

“The Garifuna say: The sea knows all our secrets, our sorrows and joys. It knows all our mysteries; it is a friend who is always there. When we were born, it was already there; when we leave, it will still be there.”

Recinos M. F. 2029

Garifuna women, an Afro-descendant people with roots in the Caribbean, have forged a rich history marked by resistance, cultural preservation, and the fight for their rights. Their presence in the Caribbean region, particularly in countries such as Honduras and Guatemala, has left an indelible mark on history and society. Morillo A. (2022) states that Garifuna culture constitutes a rich ethnic mosaic resulting from the syncretization of African, Arawak, and Carib traditions. This sociocultural group, settled primarily on the Atlantic coast of Central America, has developed a unique identity characterized by a deep connection with nature and a spirituality centered on the principle of 'Au Buni; Amürü Nuni,' which refers to universal love and veneration of a supreme deity. The Garifuna worldview is manifested in diverse cultural expressions, such as language, music, dance, and agricultural and fishing practices. These activities not only satisfy basic needs but also serve as vehicles for transmitting ancestral knowledge, strengthening community ties, and reaffirming their ethnic identity. From an anthropological perspective, Garifuna culture represents a paradigmatic case of cultural adaptation and resilience. Throughout its history, this people has managed to preserve its traditions despite the processes of colonization and globalization, becoming a benchmark in studies on mestizo identities and multiculturalism.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative methodological approach, focusing on the analysis of documentary

sources such as academic articles, books, and historical documents to explore the role of women in the construction and reproduction of their communities. Given the nature of the research, interviews or direct contact with study subjects are avoided, prioritizing the wealth of information provided by written texts. A thorough content analysis will be used, identifying patterns, recurring themes, and divergences in the representation of women in the sources consulted. This process will allow for the construction of a narrative that reveals power dynamics, resistance strategies, and women's contributions in their social contexts.

In addition, a comparative approach will be applied to contrast the perspectives of different authors and periods, seeking to identify changes and continuities in the perception of the female role. The data will be interpreted through a feminist theoretical framework, which will make visible gender inequalities and the ways in which women challenge patriarchal structures. Following Scott (1988), gender will be considered a fundamental analytical category for understanding the social relations and cultural constructions that influence women's lives. The combination of these qualitative methods will allow for a deep and nuanced analysis of women's role in building their communities, bringing new perspectives to social research.

Investigation

Flores Recinos, M. (2019) “*Matrilocalidad For the Garifuna people, women play a hierarchical role in ancestral spiritual ceremonies. These spiritual encounters are led by grandmothers called nagoto, to whom tribute is paid in the Dügü. Garifuna men know that women are chosen from generation to generation to communicate with ancestors; they safeguard ancestral knowledge vital to the life of the Garifuna people. Therefore, all authentic Garifuna people recognize and*

respect the matriarchy and the importance that these women have in the defense of the ancestral territory” (pp36-37).

The text cited above provides a profound and detailed insight into the importance of women in Garifuna culture. This people, with roots in the fusion of African, Arawak, and Carib cultures, has developed a social and spiritual system where women occupy a central and hierarchical place. The key points we can draw from the text are:

Women's Role in Ceremonies: Garifuna women, especially the grandmothers known as "nagoto," play a fundamental role in ancestral spiritual ceremonies. They guide and direct these sacred gatherings, establishing a direct connection with the ancestors.

Ancestral Knowledge: Garifuna women are considered the custodians of invaluable ancestral knowledge, which is passed down from generation to generation and is essential to the survival and identity of the Garifuna people.

Communication with Ancestors: Women are believed to have the special ability to communicate with their ancestors; this spiritual connection allows them to obtain guidance and protection for the people. **Matriarchy and Territorial Defense:** The text emphasizes the importance of matriarchy in Garifuna culture; men recognize and respect women's role as spiritual leaders and defenders of ancestral territory.

Figure 1 Garifuna Women

Garifunas carry their identity, color and culture in their clothing and accessories Honduras Tips (2022)

Characteristics and Current Situation

Hooker Blandford, A. (2014), in Garifuna and Afro-descendant cultures, women play a multifaceted and essential role, acting as pillars of intergenerational cultural transmission. Through oral tradition, music, dance, and rituals, they preserve language, spirituality, and ancestral traditions. Their leadership is manifested in community decision-making and in their role as family health care providers through the practice of traditional medicine. This central position reflects a social system where women not only preserve their cultural heritage but also exercise significant power in the cohesion and well-being of their communities.

According to Mesa Márquez (2012), the poetic production of Garifuna women writers in Central America constitutes a textual corpus that demonstrates the processes of ethnic and gender identity construction. This corpus functions as a counter-discourse that supplements the official history, rescuing and making visible the historical memory and cultural traditions of the Garifuna community. In this sense, the work of Garifuna women as cultural transmitters takes on fundamental importance, as their literary creations become a

space for representing and vindicating their experiences. Through their verses, these authors construct a narrative that transcends national borders, connecting with other Afro-descendant voices and forming a unified discourse that problematizes power relations and social inequalities. The use of Creole in Garifuna poetry is especially significant, as this language stands as a marker of identity and a vehicle for the transmission of ancestral knowledge. By using Creole, Garifuna poets reaffirm their belonging to a historically and culturally specific community, while contributing to the revitalization of their mother tongue. (pp. 252-253)

The author mentions Xiomara Mercedes Cacho Caballero, born in the Garifuna community of Punta Gorda, as a pioneer in Honduran literature. Her poetic work represents a milestone, being the first publication by a Garifuna woman, and even more so by a Black woman in Honduras. Her command of four languages and her experience in special education enrich her writing, which reflects a deep connection with her African culture and roots. According to literary critic Helen Umaña, Cacho Caballero's work stands out for its intercultural nature, combining Garifuna, Spanish, and English in her titles and poems. This linguistic fusion reflects the confluence of the diverse cultures present in her environment and represents a pioneering effort to

integrate them into Honduran poetry. Through her writing, Cacho Caballero seeks to affirm the Garifuna identity, reviving pride in her ancestors and denouncing the suffering they experienced upon arriving in the Americas. His work thus becomes a testimony of cultural resistance and a voice that makes visible the experiences of Afro-descendant communities in Honduras (pp 253-254)

Fernández Catillo K. (2017) discusses the Garifuna language, dance, and music in his article, cultural manifestations of great value, which were proclaimed by UNESCO in 2001 as a Masterpiece of the Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity. This international recognition underscored the importance of preserving this rich cultural heritage, originating in the Garifuna communities scattered across Belize, Guatemala, Honduras, Nicaragua, the United States, and Saint Vincent. Despite efforts made since then, the intergenerational transmission and everyday use of the Garifuna language face significant challenges. The lack of sound public policies and the influence of dominant languages jeopardize the long-term viability of this linguistic and cultural heritage. Studies and research carried out in recent years have shed light on the complexity of cultural transmission processes and the sociolinguistic dynamics that affect minority languages. However, it is necessary to further analyze the factors that influence the loss of speakers and develop more effective revitalization strategies. In this context, it is essential to strengthen the participation of Garifuna communities in the definition and implementation of policies to safeguard their cultural heritage. Likewise, it is essential to promote interdisciplinary research and collaboration between academics, cultural activists, and government representatives.

The National Council of Protected Areas (CONAP) (2021) stated that the Garifuna people, with their unique language and rich cultural heritage recognized in 2001 by UNESCO, have historically been marginalized in Guatemala, despite efforts to recognize their diversity. In this context, Garifuna women play a fundamental role as pillars of their community and culture. Despite facing discrimination and negative stereotypes, Garifuna women are the driving force of the local and national economy, excelling in handicrafts, gastronomy, and the transmission of ancestral traditions. Their work as weavers, dancers, entrepreneurs, and guardians of ancestral knowledge is crucial to the preservation of their identity and the sustainable development of their community.

In her article on Garifuna Women, Dance Groups, and Social Memory, Randazzo Eisemann, F. (2019), highlights the role of Garifuna songs, especially those composed by women such as the Yurumei, as much more than simple artistic expressions. They constitute a vital cultural practice that encapsulates collective and personal memory and has played a crucial role in preserving their language. As a community whose language was unwritten until recently, songs became an essential means of transmitting knowledge, values, and experiences across generations. Garifuna women, as creators and bearers of these songs, have been instrumental in revitalizing and maintaining their language,

ensuring that their rich linguistic and cultural heritage remains alive.

Initial Findings

Research converges in highlighting the multifaceted and essential role of Garifuna women as pillars of intergenerational cultural transmission. Through oral traditions, music, dance, and rituals, they preserve their language, spirituality, and ancestral traditions, exercising significant leadership in community decision-making and in family health through traditional medicine. Their poetic and literary production constitutes a counter-discourse that makes historical memory and cultural traditions visible, reclaiming their experiences and constructing a narrative that transcends borders. Furthermore, their mastery of the Garifuna language, recognized by UNESCO as intangible cultural heritage, and their work in creating songs and dances are crucial to the revitalization and maintenance of their identity. Despite the challenges they face, such as a lack of public policies and the influence of dominant languages, Garifuna women continue to be the driving force of the local and national economy, excelling in handicrafts, gastronomy, and entrepreneurship, and playing a fundamental role in the sustainable development of their communities.

Conclusions.

The history of Garifuna women is a testament to the strength and resilience of the human spirit. Their ancestral knowledge, spiritual connection, and leadership have been essential to the survival and identity of this people. They also represent a paradigmatic case of cultural syncretism, where the resilience and adaptation of African and Amerindian populations in a colonial context gave rise to a new ethnic identity, rich in traditions and rooted in the coastal territories of the Caribbean. It is essential to recognize and value the contribution of Garifuna women to society and support their efforts to preserve their culture and improve their living conditions. Studies on gender and power in Garifuna communities contribute to enriching our knowledge of the social and cultural dynamics of the region. The protection of their rights and the promotion of their development are responsibilities shared by all.

Recommendations

It is imperative to analyze the adaptation and resilience strategies deployed in the face of contemporary challenges, such as globalization, migration, and systemic discrimination, as well as the impact of public policies and social movements on the revitalization of the Garifuna language and culture, with special attention to female leadership in these processes. It is also suggested to explore the impact of public policies and social movements on the revitalization of the Garifuna language and culture, and how women lead these processes. Ultimately, the goal is to generate knowledge that contributes to the formulation of public policies that guarantee equal opportunities and respect for the rights of Garifuna women, recognizing them as key social actors in the construction of their own realities.

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